

DEVELOPMENT OF HIGH TOUGHNESS EPOXY RESINS FOR LIQUID COMPOSITE MOULDING

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SUMMARY

Epoxy matrix systems combining high toughness with rheological behaviour appropriate for liquid composite moulding are developed in this work. The neat resin and carbon laminate properties of a variety of novel formulations are evaluated and compared with reference materials to identify promising technologies for the development of advanced matrix materials suitable for infusion processing.

Keywords: One component epoxy matrix, RTM, Nanotechnology, Toughening, High Temperature Performance

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Liquid Composite Moulding

Prepregs and autoclave curing have long been the state of the art processes for manufacturing of aerospace composite parts. Very few processes can match the consistent part quality and high fiber volume of these techniques. However, autoclave processing is expensive, especially for medium- to large-size production runs. Maintenance and operating expenses tend to be higher than for ovens, presses and similar equipment. The cycle times are measured in hours and therefore larger production rates require multiple autoclaves. Finally, the size of autoclave creates limitations for the dimensions of the final composite parts.

Within the last years engineers have been searching for alternative methods that can reduce costs while maintaining the high performance of autoclave-cured parts. Liquid composite molding (LCM) technologies have shown evidence that they can provide that alternative. LCM processes are characterized by the injection of a liquid resin into a dry fiber preform, and include resin transfer molding (RTM), vacuum-assisted RTM (VARTM) and infusion processes.

1.2. Next Generation Resin Systems

Epoxy resins derive their high mechanical performance and inherent chemical and thermal resistance from cross-link density and chain rigidity. LCM processes require low viscosity, which makes the formulation aspects relating to toughening particularly challenging.

Figure 1 depicts the typical antagonistic requirements demanded by OEM's in order to expand design allowables of current and future aircrafts.

High throughput, operation at elevated temperature under aggressive conditions, impact resistance (low and high velocity), fatigue, durability, cost and of increasing concern environmental health and safety aspects must all be considered due to the significant investments needed to introduce novel technologies into the aerospace market sector.

Figure 1: Schematic presentation of the requirements of new generation resin systems.

Many studies can be found in the literature about the toughening of epoxy resins [1-4]. In the current paper, model systems were evaluated to compare state of the art nano-toughening technologies using “soft” and “hard” nanofillers solely or in combinations. From this several systems have been formulated further to develop prototype toughened matrix resins which show significant improvement relative to state of the art RTM resins.

2. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

2.1. Model systems – Nano-filled resins

2.1.1. Formulations and physical properties

The resin systems investigated in the study were mainly based on multifunctional resins (e.g. trifunctional, Araldite® MY 0510 and/or tetrafunctional, Araldite® MY 721, both from Huntsman Advanced Materials) and an aromatic based amine hardener. Different nanofillers were evaluated. The results presented in the following paragraphs focus on four of them: tri-block copolymer and a core shell rubber from the category of “soft”

nanofillers and multi-walled carbon nanotubes and a nanosilica from the category of “hard” nanofillers.

Four examples of model systems are presented in

Table 1. Systems 1 and 3 contain only “soft” nanofiller. A direct comparison of these systems shows that SBM results to a resin system with three-times higher viscosity compared to CSR. Essentially the soluble block copolymer raises viscosity in the uncured material much more drastically whereas the preformed CSR tend to swell slightly and are processed differently to ensure dispersion not dissolution in the uncured matrix. Cured specimens of both systems show spherical domains approx. 50nm or smaller (Figure 2a,c). The addition of “hard” fillers in Systems 1 and 3 (System 2 and 4 in

Table 1) leads to an increase in viscosity especially in the case of MWCNT where the viscosity is doubled. The microscopical investigation showed the formation of MWCNT aggregates in System 4 amongst the well distributed CSR nano-particles (Figure 2d).

Table 1: Composition and physical-chemical properties of four model systems.

		SYSTEM #1	SYSTEM #2	SYSTEM #3	SYSTEM #4
EP Matrix		Multifunctional epoxy resins + Reactive diluent + 4,4'-Diaminodiphenyl sulfone			
Nanofiller	V_f %	6.5% SBM	6.5 % SBM 2.2 % NSi	6.5% CSR	6.5% CSR 0.25% MWCNT
	Dimensions	-	NSi: D= 40-80nm	CSR: D= 30-60nm	MWCNT:D=15nm, L=1-10µm
	MwD	S ₁₂ B ₁₂ M ₂₂	S ₁₂ B ₁₂ M ₂₂	proprietary	-
M_c [g.mol⁻¹], theoretical		478	476	477	478
Viscosity @ 80°C [mPa.s]		300	430	100	200
Curing Cycle Process : Resin at 80°C - ramp from 120°C to 180°C at 2.5°C/min then hold for 2hrs at 180°C, then ramp down at 2.5°C/min to RT					
Degree of polymerization [%], via DSC		> 95	> 95	> 95	> 95
T_g, Onset [°C], via DMA		187	183	190	182

2.1.2. Mechanical properties

In Figure the flexural modulus and fracture energy in Mode I for the four systems are compared. The hard nano filler in System 2, nanosilica showed some improvement in flexural modulus though is marginal. The V_f however is low and more significant effects on mechanical performance has been observed at higher V_f using such technology. All four systems do show enhanced fracture performance by means of high G_{Ic} values. As benchmark, a state of the art aerospace liquid resin system exhibits a G_{Ic} value of 168 J/m². Compared to this value, an increase of 148, 132, 160 and 85%,

respectively, is achieved for the studied model systems. A large scattering in the G_{Ic} value for System 4 can be seen in Figure . This confirms the heterogeneity of this system as previously noticed in Figure 2d and with the fracture surfaces observed under mode I loading in Figure 3.

Figure 2: TEM micrographs of the four model systems: a) System 1, b) System 2, c) System 3 and d) System 4.

Figure 3: SEM micrographs of a) System 3 and b) System 4.

Figure 4: Flexural modulus and G_{Ic} values for the four model systems.

2.2 Model systems – Composites with nano-filled matrices

The model systems presented in Section 2.1 were used as matrices of carbon fiber reinforced (CFR) composites. Four plies of quadraxial non-crimp fabrics (NCF) from Saertex[®] were used as reinforced material given the final laminate lay-up of $(90/-45/0/+45/-45/0/+45/90)_2$. The composite laminates were manufactured via RTM using the following processing parameters: resin temperature 80°C, mould temperature 120°C, injection pressure 2 bars.

The Compression After Impact (CAI) test has been chosen to analyze the damage tolerance of the manufactured composite laminates. Therefore, a series of CAI specimens was prepared, impacted and tested according to AITM 1-0010. CAI specimens have dimensions of 150 x 100 mm and a thickness of about 4 mm.

The produced specimens were artificially impacted by using a drop weight tower. A guided drop weight falls from a calculated height on the clamped specimen. The impact energy depends on the mass of the drop weight as well as on the height off which the drop weight falls onto the specimen. During impact, the contact force versus time is recorded.

The impacted specimens are compression loaded until failure in order to determine their residual compression strength after impact. The specimens are laterally guided to avoid premature global buckling. The residual strength versus the impact energy is given in

Figure 3 for the laminates with the four different systems as matrices. The values for a laminate with state of the art aerospace resin matrix is shown as reference.

Figure 3: Residual compression strength after impact of composite specimens designed with different resin systems

According to DIN EN 6038 Barely Visible Impact Damages (BVID) correspond to indentation depths of 0.3 mm. The indentation of all specimens was measured after impact. It was found that an indentation of 0.3 mm corresponds to an impact energy of about 40 J. Systems 1, 2 and 3 exhibit increased CAI strength compared to the reference after a barely visible impact of 40 J as shown in

Figure 3. On the other hand, the system containing MWCNT (System 4) has the lowest values of compression strength for all impact energies. Figure 4 illustrates the fracture surfaces of laminates produced with System 3 and System 4 after Mode I loading. For System 3 where only CSR is used as toughener, a uniform distribution of the pull-out nanospheres can be observed. On the other hand, the presence of MWCNT in System 4 initiates other fracture mechanisms, probably only in microscale, due to the formation of aggregates. These mechanisms occur in lower loadings, prohibiting in this way the action of CSR and leading finally to lower CAI performance of this system.

a)

Figure 4: Mode I fracture surfaces of composite laminates manufactured with a), b) System 3 and c), d) System 4.

3. CONCLUSION

Different “soft” and “hard” nanofillers were used as tougheners for epoxy resins. The fracture energy of the resins increased significantly compared to state of the art aerospace resin. The use of MWCNT results in a lower enhanced of the fracture performance which is probably contacted to their pure dispersion quality. All systems could be processed by RTM and the final composite laminates were tested at CAI. The MWCNT containing system showed the poorest strength after compression even compared to the state of the art laminate. Block copolymer, CSR and NSi toughened systems showed enhanced performance for impact energies above 40J (corresponds to BVID).

A signification observation of this study is that the high increase in fracture energy of the nanoresins was not translated in a corresponding increase of the damage tolerance of the composites. The CAI strength was not significantly improved compared to the reference. This is most probably connected to the low modulus of the resins which is contradicts their increased toughness as shown schematically in

Figure 1.

Further to the above base models discussed in this paper, formulated matrices have been developed which show marked increase in both modulus and toughness and composite evaluation will be forthcoming later in 2009.

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